

Hamilton-Jacobi Equation and Special Relativity

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The classical formalism of Hamilton-Jacobi theory, as presented in (1), applies to many particles and contains two important equations. The first is: $\partial S/\partial t = H$, where S is called an action and H , the Hamiltonian. $H = pv - L$ for a single particle, where $L(x,v,t)$ is a function called a Lagrangian. (1) also presents the equation: $\partial S/\partial x_i = \partial L/\partial v_i = p_i$, where i represents the i th particle and one considers one dimension.

For a single particle one has the equations: $\partial S/\partial t = E$ (for $H=E$ cases) and $\partial S/\partial x = p = \partial L/\partial v$ (x component). In other words, S is a function containing E, p, x and t such that the operators $\partial/\partial t$ and $\partial/\partial x$ retrieve the important pieces of information, E and p . For a single particle, the simplest solution for S is $-Et + px$.

The above equations, however, must apply as seen in any frame moving at constant speed. If one has a rest mass, m_0 , at $x=0$ at t such that it is not moving, a person in a frame moving with constant $-v$ sees not only an $E(m_0, v)$ and p , but also a different x', t' such that $v = x'/t'$. Thus, E, p, x, t all transform when seen from a moving frame. This suggests that $-Et + px$ is an invariant of the transformation (Lorentz transformation) which describes a particle as seen from a different frame moving with constant $-v$. This means using different values for E, p than the nonrelativistic ones because $-Et + px$ suggests that (p, E) and (x, t) transform the same way.

The classical Hamiltonian-Jacobi theory predicts the metric needed to create the $-Et + px$ invariant. Given that: $H = pv - L(x, v, t)$, for a free particle with $H=E$ and $L(v)$, one also has the form of the transformation, but in general, Hamilton-Jacobi theory was developed before special relativity and so only L nonrelativistic was known. We show that one may obtain the Lorentz transformation.

In classical nonrelativistic mechanics, kinetic energy is energy, i.e. $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$. Hamilton-Jacobi theory is developed to account for this nonrelativistic view. This begs the question: Why does it also describe special relativity? For example, in the above paragraphs we use E and p , but for special relativity these are different quantities from $\frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$. In other words, how does one know that applying Hamilton-Jacobi theory to an E and p consistent with different frames leads to the nonrelativistic result? We try to answer this question in this note and argue that it is linked to the transformation properties of (p, E) and (x, t) .

Hamiltonian-Jacobi Theory

Classical Hamiltonian-Jacobi theory may be applied to many particles, but should also hold for a single particle. It seems that it was developed to handle nonrelativistic classical mechanics for which:

$$E = \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2 \quad \text{and} \quad p = m_0 v \quad ((1))$$

It uses the quantities: $S(x, t, p, E)$, $H = \text{Hamiltonian}$ and $L(x, v, t) = \text{Lagrangian}$. In addition, one has the following relations for a free particle:

$L(v)$ with $p = dL/dv$ partial and $H = E = pv - L$ ((2))

In addition, one has from (1) the important relations:

dS/dt partial = $-E$ ((3a)) and $dS/dx_i = dL/dv_i = p_i$, where i represents the i th particle and one

considers the x co-ordinate ((3b))

For a single particle, ((3b)) becomes dS/dx partial = p .

The above formalism describes nonrelativistic mechanics and it seems that a priori one would not expect it to be linked to special relativity or moving frames. At the same time, one should have the same physical equations as seen from different frames moving with constant $-v$.

It turns out, however, that $S = -Et + px$, which solves ((3a)) and ((3b)) is directly linked to special relativity if one uses E and p as special relativistic quantities: $E = \gamma m_0 c^2$ and $p = \gamma m_0 v$ and not ((1)).

We try to investigate why this is the case.

Transformations Linked to a Moving Frame

The fact that one has: dS/dt partial = E and $dS/dx = p$ for a single particle means that S associates p with x and $-E$ with t as is clear in $-Et + px$. We consider a particle with rest mass, m_0 , at rest at $x=0$ at t . In nonrelativistic classical mechanics, $E = \text{kinetic energy} = 0$ and $p = 0$ so $-Et + px$ would be 0 using nonrelativistic results.

As seen from a moving frame, however, m_0 is moving with v (so there is a nonrelativistic momentum) and a nonrelativistic kinetic energy as well. Perhaps surprisingly, there is a different x' and t' as well because $x'/t' = v$, while in the rest frame $0 = x/t$.

This presents a puzzle, we argue, because $E_{\text{nonrel}} = 0$, $p_{\text{nonrel}} = 0$ transform to KE and p_{nonrel} in a different way from x and t . One may use a 2×2 matrix to describe the change of (x, t) to (x', t') such that $x'/t' = v$, but this matrix would not transform $(KE=0, p=0)$. This would suggest that (p, E) and (x, t) transform in different ways.

If, however, one could define p and E differently, $-Et + px$ would represent what appears to be an inner product with an usual $-1, 1$ metric. For $-Et + px$, (p, E) and (x, t) are treated similarly. In such a case, the Hamiltonian-Jacobi action would be an invariant and dS/dt partial = $-E$ and dS/dx partial = p would hold in any frame. This, however, would mean that the nonrelativistic expressions for E and p would not longer be the E and p used which is a problem in itself.

Perhaps a starting point for arguing that p, E and x, t should transform in the same is:

$x = vt$ for v constant and p momentum is proportional to $m_0 v$ ((3))

If a matrix transforms (x, t) , the same matrix in principle could transform p, E with these values not really being known.

The goal is then to find a matrix which transforms $(x=0, t)$ to (x', t') such that $x'/t' = v$.

The matrix seems to be:

$$\begin{pmatrix} g(v) & v g(v) \\ v g & g(v) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Here $g(v)$ is unknown. One assigns $v g(v) = a_{12}$ a priori. The $a_{22} = g(v)$ result follows from $x'/t' = v$ when one transforms from $(x=0, t)$. $a_{11} = g(v)$ follows from using the transformation with $v \rightarrow -v$. $A_{12} = \pm v g(v)$ may be assigned to give the matrix symmetry. Using $t = a_{12} g v t + g g t$ shows that $a_{12} = g(v)$ where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2}$ where b is a velocity upper limit. Applying these results to $(0, m_0 v)$ yields: $E = m_0 b^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2}$.

This result then yields $E = m_0 b^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$ as a $v \ll b$ limit, i.e. nonrelativistic.

Thus, the problem of two sets of E, p is solved by having an upper bound velocity b and describing nonrelativistic physics as satisfying $v \ll b$.

As a result, the action in Hamilton-Jacobi theory represents a Lorentz invariant because p, E and x, t transform in the same way when viewed from a frame moving with constant $-v$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Hamilton-Jacobi theory, which was designed for nonrelativistic physics, leads to an action $S = -Et + px$ for a single particle where $E = .5 m_0 v^2$ and $p = m_0 v$. In this note, we consider the rest case of m_0 at $x=0, v=0$ at t . Using nonrelativistic results, $E(\text{nonrel}) = 0$ and $p(\text{nonrel}) = 0$, while $x=0$ and one has t . In a moving frame, there is kinetic energy and p nonrel as well as x', t' such that $x'/t' = v$. This suggests that x, t and p, E transform in different ways, but $S = -Et + px$ puts them on the same footing mathematically and is of the form of a kind of inner product with a special $-1, 1$ metric. This, we argue, suggests that one seeks different E, p values from the nonrelativistic ones such that (x, t) and (p, E) transform under the same 2×2 matrix. This leads to the Lorentz matrix by simply considering $x=0, t$ transforming to x', t' with $x'/t' = v$ and the reverse transformation. This leads to a cutoff velocity b appearing in the matrix. Using this matrix, one may find that $E = m_0 b^2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2}$ and $p = m_0 v / \sqrt{1 - v^2/b^2}$ where b is the velocity cutoff. For $v \ll b$, one has the nonrelativistic results except that $E = m_0 b^2 + .5 m_0 v^2$.

Thus, if one takes $-Et + px$ serious and argues that one should have a theory that holds as seen from any frame moving with constant v , then (p, E) and (x, t) seem to transform in the same way and one is forced to use different expressions from the nonrelativistic ones for (p, E) .

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hamilton%E2%80%93Jacobi_equation